

Supporting Information

PEGylated Bottom-Up Synthesised Graphene Nanoribbons Loaded with Camptothecin as Potential Drug Carriers

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Table of Contents

1. Materials, Chemicals and Equipment	S2
2. Fourier-transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)	S2
3. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)	S3
4. Experimental details	S3
4.1 Purification of GNR-PEG and GNR-PEG-FA by dialysis monitor by TGA	S3
4.2 Calculation of grafting percentage of PEG and PEG-FA on GNR	S3
4.3 Quantification of CPT loaded on GNR-FA-PEG and GNR-PEG	S4
4.4 Folate receptor alpha quantification by flow cytometry	S5
4.5 Absorption spectra of GNR-PEG derivatives.	S9
4.6 Temperature profiles of GNR-PEG derivatives under NIR irradiation	S10
4.7 Aggregation study after laser irradiation in water by DLS	S11
4.8 Overview of relevant DDSs with PTT capability.	S13

1. Materials, Chemicals and Equipment

The materials used in this work for synthesis of GNR, GNR-PEG and GNR-PEG-FA were purchased from Alfa Aesar, Admas-beta and J&K suppliers and used as received, unless otherwise mentioned.

A549 (human epithelial cells, lung, carcinoma) and MCF-7 (human epithelial cells, breast, adenocarcinoma) were purchased from the Health Protection Agency, European collection of cell cultures (ECACC), whilst all media and media components and buffers were from Merck. Mouse anti-Human Folate Receptor alpha Monoclonal Antibody (cat no. MA5-23917), and goat anti-Mouse Secondary Antibody Alexa Fluor® 647 conjugate (cat no. A-21235), were purchased by Thermofisher. A549 and MCF-7 were cultivated at 37 °C and humidified atmosphere (5 % CO₂, 95 % air), in RPMI 1640 and DMEM media respectively, both supplemented with 10 % FBS, 1 % L-glutamine and 1 % Penicillin/Streptomycin. Cells were refreshed every 2-3 days and regularly checked for the absence of contaminations.

The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed under N₂ atmosphere from 100 - 700 °C with a 10 K/min gradient. The data were processed with Trios software. Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) was conducted on a Malvern Zetasizer Nano S apparatus with a 10 mW laser ($\lambda = 633$ nm). The measurements were performed with back scatter under room temperature. The ZS XPLORER program was used for the processing of the data. UV-visible spectra were performed in a Beckman spectrophotometer.

2. Fourier-transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

Figure S1. FTIR spectra of (a) GNR-COOH, (b) GNR-PEG, (c) GNR-PEG-FA, (d) CPT, (e) CPT@GNR-PEG, and (f) CPT@GNR-PEG-FA.

3. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Figure S2. Averaged TGA profiles of GNR-COOH, GNR-PEG, and GNR-PEG-FA, respectively, 100 °C to 700 °C under N₂ atmosphere.

4. Experimental details

4.1 Purification of GNR-PEG and GNR-PEG-FA by dialysis monitor by TGA

To confirm the unreacted PEG and PEG-FA is removed from GNR-PEG and GNR-PEG-FA, respectively, we calculated the standard deviations (SDs) of the weight loss for GNR-PEG and GNR-PEG-FA residues by TGA (Figure S2, Table 1). The resulting dispersions of GNR-FA-PEG and GNR-PEG after amide bond formation were purified by centrifugation-filtration (4000 rpm, 40 min, with 10 KDa membrane) to remove unreacted FA-PEG and PEG, respectively. Each time, the GNR samples were freeze-dried and followed by TGA, until the standard deviation of their weight loss between 100 and 500 °C were less than 5% for the last three times. In particular, the SDs of GNR-PEG and GNR-PEG-FA residues are 3.9% and 3.3% (shown in Table 1), respectively. Considering the SD of pristine GNR-COOH was 1.5% and the water residue may be trapped in GNR-PEG and GNR-PEG-FA during the dialysis and centrifuged filtration, the small SDs of functional GNR confirm that non-covalent PEG has been successfully washed away, or the values of SDs would be much bigger.

4.2 Calculation of grafting percentage of PEG and PEG-FA on GNR

The grafting percentage (GP) of PEG on GNR was obtained according to the previous report by applying the following equations:^[1]

$$W_{PEG} = 1 - W_{residue} \times \frac{185 \times 4}{948} - W_{residue} \quad Eq. S1$$

$$GP = \frac{W_{PEG}/2000}{(W_{residue}/948) \times 4} \times 100\% \quad Eq. S2$$

Where the W_{PEG} denotes the weight fraction of the PEG chains, $W_{residue}$ is the weight fraction of the GNR rigid backbone, which still retained after thermal treatment over 500 °C according to the TGA curve; 948, 185 and 2000 represent the molar mass of GNR backbone, $(CH_2)_{10}CONH$ and PEG, respectively.

The GP of PEG-FA on GNR was obtained by the following equations:

$$P_{residue} = \frac{948 + 0.49 \times 441x}{948 + 4 \times 185 + 2441x} \quad Eq. S3$$

$$GP = \frac{x}{4} \times 100\% \quad Eq. S4$$

In one unit of GNR-2000-FA, there is 1 GNR rigid backbone (948), 4 units of $(CH_2)_{10}CONH$ (185), and x units of PEG2000-FA (2441 x). At 500 °C, the residue of PEG is almost 0 and that of FA is 49%, grafting percentage is $x/4$. $P_{residue}$ is the residue percentage at 500 °C obtained by TGA.

4.3 Quantification of CPT loaded on GNR-FA-PEG and GNR-PEG

The capability of GNR-FA-PEG or GNR-PEG to carry CPT was evaluated in terms of loading capability (LC%) and the loading efficiency (LE%, details in supporting information). LC% is the amount of drug loaded per unit weight of DDS, indicating the percentage of DDS mass that is due to the adsorbed drug. The mass percentage of the drug in the DDS to the total amount of the drug used to prepare the system is known as LE%.

Firstly, the amount of CPT in the eluent after filtration was calculated by the UV-vis absorption of CPT at 369 nm according to Lambert-Beer's law (Fig. S2). The amount of CPT loaded on GNR materials was then obtained by subtracting the amount of CTP of washing eluents to the total CPT used for the preparation of the DDSs.

Figure S2. Fitting curve of CPT concentration against absorption.

Finally, LC% LE% were obtained in accordance with the following equations:

$$LC\% = \frac{W_{CPT}^0 - W_{CPT}^{eluent}}{W_{GNR}} \times 100 \quad Eq. S5$$

$$LE\% = \frac{W_{CPT}^0 - W_{CPT}^{eluent}}{W_{CPT}^0} \times 100 \quad Eq. S6$$

Where, W_{CPT}^0 , W_{CPT}^{eluent} , and W_{GNR} are the weight of the drug initially added, the weight of the drug in the eluent, and the total weight of GNR, respectively.

4.4 Folate receptor alpha quantification by flow cytometry

A549 and MCF-7 were selected as negative and positive folate receptor alpha (FR-alpha) cell lines, respectively. The FR-alpha expression was evaluated on both cell lines by flow cytometry. Cells were harvested and concentration was adjusted to 5×10^6 cell/mL. 200 μ L of cell suspensions were transferred to each tube and medium was removed. Cells were resuspended in 100 μ L of FR-alpha antibody solution (2 μ g/mL in incubation buffer) and incubated 30 minutes in dark on ice. Cells were washed 3 times with washing buffer, resuspended and incubated 30 minutes in dark on ice with Goat anti-Mouse Secondary Antibody Alexa Fluor® 647 conjugate solution (5 μ g/mL in incubation buffer). Cells were washed 3 times with washing buffer, resuspended and incubated 15 minutes in 100 μ L of formalin. After fixation, cells were washed and resuspended in 250 μ L of PBS. The samples were analysed using a flow cytometer with APC detector (filter 660/20).

Flow cytometry studies of level of FA receptor expression

Figure S3. Flow cytometry studies of level of FA receptor expression in MCF-7 and A549.

Cytotoxicity by MTT assay

Figure S4. Cytotoxicity by MTT assay of different concentrations of free CPT, GNR-PEG and GNR-PEG-FA and the corresponding hybrids CPT@GNR-PEG and CPT@GNR-PEG-FA, in A549 cell lines. 24, 48 and 72 h were used as incubation times. The concentrations reported refer to CPT (in mM) and cell viability is in percentage respect the control (untreated cells). Tables report IC₅₀ values for each CPT containing compound. Each graph was generated with GraphPad Prism 9.1.0 from the average of triplicates from at least 2 independent experiments. The multiple comparisons were performed by a two-way ANOVA analysis followed by Tukey's multiple comparison post-hoc test. Significance was graphically indicated as follows: *P*: P<0.05, **: P<0.01, ***: P<0.001, ****: P<0.0001.

4.5 Absorption spectra of GNR-PEG derivatives.

Figure S5. (a) UV-vis absorption of GNR-PEG, CPT@GNR-PEG dispersions in water (0.5 mg/ml) and CPT in EtOH, b) GNR-PEG-FA, CPT@GNR-PEG-FA in water (0.5 mg/ml), compared to CPT in EtOH.

4.6 Temperature profiles of GNR-PEG derivatives under NIR irradiation

Figure S6. Temperature profile for GNR derivatives during the laser irradiation. Solution of GNR derivatives (0.5 mg/mL) in water were irradiated with 808 nm laser (1W power). The solutions were irradiated for 3 minutes (red section), followed by 3 minutes temperature recording in dark (gray section).

4.7 Aggregation study after laser irradiation in water by Dynamic Light Scattering

Figure S7. (a) DLS plots of GNR-PEG, (b) CPT@ GNR-PEG, (c) GNR-PEG-FA, (d) CPT@GNR-PEG-FA dispersions in water (0.25 mg/mL) before (solid line) and after irradiation (dash line).

4.8 Overview of relevant drug delivery systems with photothermal capability.

Table S1. Summary table of the most relevant graphene-based DDs for PPT. NGO: nanographene oxide; NrGO: nano reduced graphene oxide, GONr: graphene oxide nanoribbon.

Entry	Graphene derivative	Synthetic approach	Drug	LC%	LE%	T (°C)	Ref
1	PEGylated nanographene oxide (NGO-PEG-DOX)	Top-down	DOX	142.5		51	[1]
2	Reduced PEGylated nanosized graphene oxide (RV-NrGO/PEG)	Top-down	RV	175.6		60	[2]
3	CuS nanoparticles-decorated graphene oxide functionalized with polyethylene glycol (PEG-GO/CuS)	Top-down	DOX		90.0	46-55	[3]
4	Reduced Graphene Oxide/Mesoporous Silica/Hyaluronic Acid Nanocomposite (rGO-PDA@MS/Ce6/HA)	Top-down	Ce6	60.5		35	[4]
5	Octreotide-PEG Conjugated Nanographene Oxide (NGO-PEG-OCT)	Top-down	DOX	137		60	[5]
6	IR780-reduced graphene oxide (IR780-rGO-HA)	Top-down	DOX	300	37.4 - 77.4	59	[6]
7	Hyaluronic Acid-Decorated Graphene Oxide (HSG)	Top-down	DOX	49	49.3	72	[7]
8	MNR13-GONR	Top-down	Metformin	-	-	-	[8]
9	PL-PEG-GONRs/DOX	Top-down	DOX	308.9	70.4-30.9	45-50	[9]
10	TMP/PEG-pyr/Gal-pyr/GNR-PEO	Bottom-up	TMP	69.1	69.7	-	[10]
11	Graphdiyne Nanosheet (DOX/GDY)	Bottom-up	DOX	38.0	75-30	52	[11]
12	Graphene nanoribbons PEG ₂₀₀₀ -FA (GNR-PEG-FA)	Bottom-up	CPT	71.2	71.3	41-42	This work

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